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Hnf4a is a non-classical autoimmune regulator that functions in organ-specific negative selection.

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We discovered a novel organ-specific TRA regulatory control function for Hnf4a based on our discovery of TRA presentation as a means of immune surveillance evasion. We distinguished this function from a general TRA function (e.g., AIRE) and from liver- organogenesis specific functions of other Hnf-related factors.

Results

It was possible their expression was based on tissue-specific organogenesis processes that rely on or are intrinsically associated with expression of hepatic-enriched genes; their expression could also have been a mechanism by which the tumor evades immune surveillance in the liver by selective activation of TRA during liver metastasis from the breast.

Distinguishing a bona fide TRA from other genes that are tissue-specific and self-derived but do not function in thymic instruction of self for organ-specific tolerance and thus lack TRA function despite tissue-specific expression requires detection of TRA depletion in mTEC from AIRE knock-out mice or cells with deletion of AIRE indicating capacity to function as a TRA during thymocyte negative selection.

SEEK: AIRE, AIRE and FEZF2 or AIRE, FEZF2 and MUC1, MUC20 and CEACAM5

2. The fibrinogen family FGA, FGG and FGB and the albumin (ALB) protein are bona fide TRA.

GSE14365

mTEC vs. mTEC AIRE -/-

Epithelial cells from the medulla of the thymus (mTEC) where negative selection occurs with AIRE-mediated TRA presentation, when obtained from mice lacking AIRE were absent or deficient in production of FGG, FGA and FGB, as well as albumin.

We concluded fibrinogens and albumin were thus bona fide TRA, expressed in the thymus but for thymic instruction of self in the liver, and required AIRE for TRA induction.

Albumin, FGG, FGB and FGA were likely selectively re-activated for evasion of tumor surveillance that might occur during metastasis to a distant organ site (e.g., the primary tumor in the breast and the metastasis derived from that tumor in the liver).

3. Systems biologic identification of genes with putative TRA function.

We performed discovery of nuclear factors with tissue-restricted antigen (TRA) activation potential using system-wide transcriptional co-regulation by AIRE and Fezf2 transcriptional networks.

To enhance likelihood of target retrieval without introducing prohibitive bias we used in conjunction with AIRE and Fezf2 a limited set of genes described as TRA: mucins Muc1 and Muc4, and Ceacam5.

We identified Hnf4a as a nuclear factor with suspected transactivation potential similar to AIRE and Fezf2.

4. Hnf4A has TRA potential.

We studied Hnf4a function in cells containing one mutant copy of Hnf4a generated in induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS) differentiated in vitro to beta cells.

GSE188827

IPS with Hnf4a+/c811dupA corrected (control)

IPS with Hnf4a+/c811dupA

Cells deficient in Hnf4a expressed a relatively large collection of TRA. We studied Hnf4a transactivation capacity heterologously in iPS-derived beta cells which added complexity to study of a factor with suspected TRA activation potential which we surmised was tissue-specific for instruction of hepatic

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tolerance but thymic (central tolerance). TRAs controlled by AIRE in the mTEC represent self antigen from multiple organ sites including the pancreas (INS and GCG) and brain and CNS (PKP4 and GAD1) (Figure 3).